

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR INCREASING WOMEN'S INTEREST IN SOCIAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *The article discusses about the reforms aimed at increasing the social activity of women in the Republic of Uzbekistan and their activities in leadership positions. In addition, the fact that our mothers and grandmothers were the first promoters of high spirituality and love for books is reflected in today's problems and their solutions.*

Keywords: *women, family strengthening, enlightened mothers, child rearing, parental responsibility, increasing reading, reading Mother's Day.*

It is a clear fact that the spiritual level of any nation is first determined by the spiritual level of the women of this country" [1]. It is related to the combination of safety-related factors that determine the level of quality in various aspects of a country and society. However, in today's age of highly developed modern information and communication technologies, it has become an urgent task to strengthen the enthusiasm of not only young people around the world, but also many adults, especially our mothers and women, to read books.

The President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the ceremony dedicated to the International Women's Day has deep content and meaning: "If one girl in the family studies gets a higher education, a modern profession, the atmosphere in the house changes completely" [2].

In our independent country, we are focusing on improving the quality of education and training of women. As the great thinker Abdurauf Fitrat said, "Mothers are educators of all mankind." In fact, it is natural for a girl in the family to study, to get her education, to have a modern profession, and to change the whole atmosphere in the house. To this end, we were all pleased with the adoption, under the leadership of the head of state, of an important program aimed at supporting women's education and increasing their social activity.

Strengthening families, increasing the responsibility of parents in raising children is considered one of the urgent issues today. In this regard, the President proposed the organization of the "Smart Women" movement consisting of reputable and educated women. This movement should become the "conscience of the neighborhood". Because an enlightened society cannot be built without enlightened mothers, - said Shavkat Mirziyoev [3].

Today, in our society, many times more effective work is being done in promoting reading and improving reading culture than ever before. Therefore, the improvement of reading culture in the family environment cannot be said to be satisfactory. It is a pity that we also meet the family environment of product accessories along with book-loving families.

It is known that our country has adopted a Presidential Decree "On measures to radically improve activities in the field of supporting women and girls and strengthening the institution of family." Over the past short period, within the framework of this Decree, 1 Decree, 2 resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 6 resolutions and 4 orders of our government were adopted [4].

In turn, in order to bring the development and support of reading culture in Uzbekistan to a new level, develop effective solutions to problems related to the infrastructure and reading

education system, based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. No. 781 of December 14, 2020 "National program for development and support of reading culture for 2020-2025". It should also be noted that the National Program for the Development and Support of Culture was adopted [5] and the Road Map for its implementation was approved.

Based on this program, starting from 2021, every year in the first week of April in Uzbekistan, in the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the Information and Mass Communications Agency under the Presidential Administration of the Republic of Uzbekistan in cooperation with a number of interested organizations under the slogan "Book-loving nation" "Book-reading week" at a high level leads to an increase in the number of book lovers and an increase in reading culture.

In our country, especially in recent years, significant reforms have been implemented in this direction, and special importance is attached to strengthening the role of women in social and political life. As a result, today women are increasingly occupying leading positions in all spheres of our society's life, making a significant contribution to the development of education, culture and science.

If in 2017 the share of women in management was 27%, today it has increased to 33%, from 40% to 47% in political parties, from 21% to 37% in entrepreneurship. About 2,000 women are serving in leadership positions in state and public organizations. In particular, 33% of the deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis, 25% of the members of the Senate and local councils are women [6].

If 6 years ago, 110,000 women studied at universities, now this number has increased almost 5 times and is 500,000. Thus, we can say that the percentage of girls among students receiving higher education has reached 50%, an unprecedented result in history.

According to the new regulation, more than 68 billion soums of contract money was paid by the state for more than 10 thousand female students studying at the master's degree, and more than 65 thousand female students were allocated interest-free educational loans of about 727 billion soums, which is a sign of increasing their social activity. Otherwise, almost 2,000 girls living in needy families, as well as more than 500 women with five years of work experience, were admitted to universities based on a special quota. figures, popular culture and art, and sports representatives..." [7] will create a solid foundation for the performance.

According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation of the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the year "Focus on people and quality education", the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 and the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan in accordance with the tasks, 100 goals aimed at further raising the standard of living of the population, aligning the quality of education with advanced international standards, achieving sustainable economic growth and bringing our reforms to a new level to reduce poverty are envisaged.

The 72nd goal of this important document: To provide information and library services to the population, popularize reading and realize the national idea of "Book-loving nation" [8]:

➤ implementation of effective and effective ways of promoting reading in the regions.
Development of a plan of measures for holding reading events;

➤ creation of favorable conditions and infrastructure in this direction in the regions; organization of reading events at a high level as a celebration of literature and reading with the participation of famous artists and intellectuals;

➤ "Book-loving nation" is more important as it is based on the organization of educational events, book fairs, book festivals and "Book Caravan" promotions.

In particular, Goal 69 [9]:

➤ support women and girls, ensure their active participation in society;

➤ to create an environment of intolerance towards oppression and violence against women in the society, to ensure the rights and legal interests of women;

➤ to continue the policy of ensuring gender equality, to increase the socio-political activity of women, to implement reforms to support them;

➤ a number of important tasks have been set, such as providing women with education and professional skills, providing them with all-round assistance in finding a decent job, supporting their entrepreneurship, identifying talented young women and directing their abilities in the right way.

The family environment and family values play the role of the main tool in the development of a person as a highly spiritual, broad-minded person, in a word, in all-round improvement.

After all, the wise words of our great grandfather Mahmudhoja Behbudi, "While developed nations are educated by their mothers, we must first educate our mothers and teach them the language, because our knowledge and lack of language are from them" [10], is in the mind of every person who reads, our people: "The one whose father is educated." it is natural that the winged words "one reads, everyone whose mother reads, reads".

As our head of state noted: "In particular, love for reading, literature, art and sports should become an integral part of the life of our youth. As you know, we have recently adopted new decisions and programs to strengthen spiritual and educational activities in the life of our society. In their full implementation, we will first of all rely on you, the activity of our honorable women, your high intellectual potential, knowledge and experience" [11].

Reading culture also has its own standards and requirements. With this in mind, it is important for our wise mothers, young mothers and daughters to follow the following recommendations in order to have a family reading culture:

➤ always be an example to children in reading books;

➤ to have the culture of book selection;

➤ to start reading books in turn at certain times in the family circle;

➤ pay particular attention to children's memorization of poems, as it is important to strengthen memory, to achieve at least 2 poems in a month;

➤ providing books for gifts, taking into account the age, character, and spiritual world of each child;

➤ to choose works for younger children, which are more colorful pictures, written in large letters, which can reflect the boundaries of his innocent imagination;

➤ for a middle-aged reading child, to recommend works that reflect the fate of heroes of his age, describe real life, fantasy-fantasy events, and revive emotional experiences;

- to have frequent conversations about book reading with older independent, married children and give necessary recommendations, this process lays the groundwork for continuing the tradition of family reading as a sacred value and turning it into a tradition on a regular basis;
- setting the daily and weekly amounts for each book reading and regularly monitoring and organizing interviews based on the works read;
- to organize a round discussion in the family under the motto "We read together", "We are family readers" about the content of the read work, the characters' characteristics, the author's approach, the received impressions;
- specially encourage the reading child who reads on time and at the required level;
- to deal with a child who does not show enough interest in reading fiction, who cannot complete assignments on time, to develop his reading skills;
- to gain value as a highly spiritual, intellectually capable family that makes a worthy contribution to the material and spiritual development of our country.

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